

FAMILY CRUCIFERAE JUSS. (BRASSICACEAE BURNETT.) OF ALTAI MOUNTAIN COUNTRY

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Dataset on GBIF

Access to the dataset

Description

The dataset contains an up-to-date list of taxa of the family Cruciferae Juss. (Brassicaceae Burnett.) of Altai Mountain Country (AMC; <http://altaiflora.asu.ru>). It is intended to provide all interested users of GBIF with the data on the distribution of the taxa included within AMC, location of herbarium material and other types of relevant information.

As AMC is shared by four countries, national and regional treatments were considered, such as Malyshev & Peshkova (1994), Abdulina (1999), Zhou et al. (2001), German (2015), etc. Taxonomic frame for the Cruciferae of AMC was published (German, 2010), and a number of subsequent changes as well as floristic updates were taken into consideration. Current list includes 65 genera and 183 species.

Geographic scope.

The database contains information on the distribution of the family Cruciferae Juss. (Brassicaceae Burnett.) of the Altai Mountain Country (AMC) within the territories of Russia, Mongolia, China and Kazakhstan.

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